

Species 1: *H. timareta*

NOT test

Species 2: *H. melpomene*

Environmental overlap

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D= 0.09

Background 2→1

Background 1→2

Species 1: *H. timareta***NOT test****Species 2: *H. melpomene*****Equivalency**

Niche Similarity:
D = 0.111

